

Optimal Sizing of Hybrid High-Energy/High-Power Battery Energy Storage Systems to Improve Battery Cycle Life and Charging Power in Electric Vehicle Applications

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Abstract: Design of the Electric Vehicle (EV) battery pack involves different requirements related to the driving range, acceleration, fast-charging, lifetime, weight, volume, etc. Therefore, sizing of the EV battery pack necessitates a multi-objective optimization study to achieve the right trade-off considering the aforementioned factors. This “trade-off” can vary depending on the type and size of the EV, as well as use cases. In this regard, a nice solution is to use a hybridized battery pack consisting of both High-Energy (HE) and High-Power (HP) battery cells, which will help to meet a wider range of customer requirements. Hybridization decouples energy and power and thus increases design flexibility to achieve a better trade-off for a wider range of EV applications. This paper proposes an effective framework for optimal sizing of such hybridized battery packs for a typical EV, namely the Mitsubishi MiEV. Lithium-ion cells with Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide (NMC) and Lithium Titanate Oxide (LTO) chemistry are chosen as HE and HP cells, respectively. A detailed analysis is fulfilled to determine the best hybridization topology, e.g. voltage profile, interface with DC-link, etc. The genetic algorithm is used to solve the multi-objective optimization problem considering two different driving cycles, namely the New European Driving Cycle (NEDC) and Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicle Test Procedure (WLTP). The results favor the usefulness of the hybrid battery pack to simultaneously achieve lifetime and charge power requirements compared to mono battery systems. The hybrid pack offers >+40,000 km improvement in the achievable driving when an end-of-life criterion of 70% for the cell capacity is considered. Remarkably, the optimized hybrid pack can also be fast charged up to 70% within six minutes.

Keywords: Electric Vehicle (EV), Design Optimization, Hybrid Battery Pack, High-Energy Cell, High-Power Cell, Genetic Algorithm

Nomenclature

Acronyms	Definition
BMS	Battery Management System
C-rate	Charge or discharge current divided by nominal capacity
CC	Coulomb Counting
DoD	Depth-of-Discharge
EV	Electric Vehicle
EMS	Energy Management System
ESS	Energy Storage System
ECM	Equivalent Circuit Model
FTP	Federal Test Procedure
HE	High-Energy
HP	High-Power
HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
LFP	Lithium Iron Phosphate
LMO	Lithium Manganese Oxide
LTO	Lithium Titanate Oxide
Li-iron	Lithium-ion
MPC	Model Predictive Control
NEDC	New European Drive Cycle
NMC	Nickel Manganese Cobalt
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
PMSM	Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor
RWD	Rear Wheel Drive
SoC	State-of-Charge
TMS	Thermal Management System
UDDS	Urban Dynamometer Driving Schedule
WLTP	World harmonized Light-duty vehicles Test Procedure
Symbols	Definition
A_f	Frontal area of the EV
$Ah_{throughput}$	Charged/discharged ampere-hour of battery
C_d	Coefficient of the drag force
C_F	Cost function
E	Energy
F_a	Aerodynamic force
F_d	Driving force
F_g	Gradient force of the road
F_r	Rolling resistance force
F_t	Transient force
g	Gravitational constant
H	Desired driving range
i	Battery current
I_{rate}	Charge/discharge rate of battery
J	Objective function
J_{wheel}	Inertia of the wheel
k	Sample index
K_r	Rolling resistance coefficient
m	EV overall mass
N_{cycle}	Number of drive cycle iterations
N_{rate}	Number of C-rates in the drive cycle
N_t	Number of chromosomes (population size)
$N_{p,HE}$	Number of parallel HE cells
$N_{p,HP}$	Number of parallel HP cells

$N_{s,HE}$	Number of series HE cells
$N_{s,HP}$	Number of series HP cells
P	Power
Q	Rated capacity of the battery
R	Internal resistance of the battery
r_{wheel}	Tire radius
s	Second
t	Time
T	Temperature
T_d	Driving torque
T_{Motor}	Output torque of the motor
v	Linear speed of the EV
$V_{DC-link}$	DC-link voltage
$V_{HP,rated}$	Rated voltage of the HP cell
V_{OC}	Open-circuit voltage of battery
Vol	Volume
V_t	Battery terminal voltage
Greek letters	Definition
α	Weighting coefficient in the objective function
β	Weighting coefficient in the objective function
γ	Weight of design targets
η	Coulombic efficiency
θ	Slope angle of the road
ξ	Efficiency of the interface DC-DC converter
ω	Rotational velocity of the wheel
λ	Tire slip
ρ	Air density
Subscripts	Definition
ch	Charge
$Demand$	Demanded power or energy
HE	High energy
HP	High power
$Loss$	Capacity loss
max	Maximum
$pack$	Battery variables at pack level
ref	Reference

1- Introduction

Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries are mostly designed to deliver either high energy or high power depending on the type of application, e.g. Electric Vehicles (EVs) or Hybrid EVs (HEVs), respectively. High-Energy (HE) batteries are produced with thick electrodes to store a large amount of active material, which consequently increases the energy content and the driving range. In contrast, High-Power (HP) cells use thin electrodes to reduce the internal resistance thereby improving the power capability and acceleration. It is difficult to simultaneously achieve high energy and power densities within a single battery [1]. Therefore, in order to meet the concurrent energy and power requirements for different EVs and driving conditions, the battery pack of the

EV should be over-designed in terms of power (when only HP cells are used) or energy (in the case of HE cells alone). This results in a non-optimal design and oversizing of the battery pack causing additional weight, volume, and cost. Mono battery systems also face challenges such as relatively short lifetimes and poor performance, e.g. at low-temperature conditions or high charge/discharge rates [2]. A cell replacement concept has been proposed in [3] to improve the total number of cycles of the battery pack. While this idea improves the cost-effectiveness of the pack's design it doesn't offer an extension of individual cells' lifetime. To address this issue and improve the overall pack's performance, an effective solution is to use a hybridized Energy Storage System (ESS) that combines the benefits of both HE and HP batteries. The battery hybridization concept has different advantages [4] including the following:

- “Energy” and “power” can be decoupled in the design process, which means the pack can be flexibly sized based on the explicit power and energy requirements of the EV without over-designing. It will also be easier to meet a wider range of design requirements, such as the simultaneous need for faster refueling (high power) and a longer driving range (high energy) due to the use of complementary features of individual batteries.
- High C-rates (charge or discharge currents with respect to the nominal capacity) on HE cells can be shaved or shifted toward the HP cells. In other words, the HP cells can act as shock-absorbers mitigating the electrical stresses on the HE cells, which will enhance the overall lifetime. This also means reduced thermal stress on the HE cells, which can reduce the overall cost of the Thermal Management System (TMS) [5].
- The depth of discharge determines the number of chemical battery cycles. For some energy consumed, the HE cell has a lower rate of discharge than the HP cell, and by lowering the HE cells discharge, the longer the battery will last.

Hybridization is not a new concept and its benefits for designing optimal storage systems have been discussed in several works [6, 7]. Strong evidence shows the usefulness of this idea, for example, to improve lifetime [8] or increase the efficiency of regenerative braking [9]. The majority of the works have considered using batteries together with a second type of ESS, e.g. supercapacitors [10, 11], flywheels [12], and fuel cells [13]. In some works, the hybridization of more than two types of ESSs has also been discussed [14]. However, combining batteries with other types of ESSs will increase the design and production costs due to the extra effort required to integrate two different ESS technologies. Furthermore, some of the ESSs do not have enough industrialization maturity compared to the electrochemical batteries. For instance, no international

standard has yet been established to integrate supercapacitors in EVs [15]. Likewise, flywheels are complex and relatively large, which makes them useful only in applications where there is sufficient space to accommodate them, e.g. in railway transportation systems [16]. Therefore, to facilitate the industrialization of the hybridization concept, it is better to combine the same type of ESSs, for example, HE and HP electrochemical batteries. Nevertheless, this idea has only recently been discussed within the related research literature and the findings are briefly reviewed in the following:

The potential for the use of two different battery systems in EV applications has been previously outlined by Wegmann *et al.* [17, 18]. In [17], HE cells with NCA-graphite and HP cells with LTO chemistry were combined and a set of operation strategies have been recommended to improve the lifetime of the HE cells by the appropriate shifting of transients toward the HP battery. Likewise, in [18], a study to combine solid-state lithium metal polymer battery (Li/LFP) with LTO HP cells has been carried out, which showed 3.7 times higher discharge power capability and additional driving distance of up to 12.8% compared to the single-cell battery system. Passive hybridization by direct parallelization of Nickel Cobalt Manganese Oxide (NMC) HE cells with Lithium Manganese Oxide (LMO) HP cells has been fulfilled in [19]. While it was concluded that the hybrid module improves the power capability due to the overall lower achievable internal resistance, this type of hybridization results in some recovery current transients immediately after the discharge of HP cells under strong current load conditions. Energy management of hybrid battery systems has also been discussed in [20-23]. In [20], the deep deterministic policy gradient approach has been used to establish a cloud-based multi-objective Energy Management System (EMS) that aims to minimize the overall aging cost of the battery. Deep reinforcement learning-based energy management of hybrid battery systems has also been studied in [21] with the intent of improving system efficiency. Two EMSs based on deterministic dynamic programming and stochastic dynamic programming optimization have been proposed in [22, 23] to improve the energy efficiency of the hybrid battery pack as well as to reduce micro cycles on the HE cells.

The above works have focused on either assessing the usefulness of the hybrid battery concept or on specific operating aspects such as optimal energy management. However, some aspects yet have to be addressed in more detail. Particularly, a model-based design optimization approach is required to determine the best sizes and configurations of the HE and HP batteries in the hybrid battery system. Such model-based design should be able to appropriately translate the EV real driving cycles to battery pack duty cycles to examine different performances with regard to different design targets such as driving range and lifetime. To date, the dimensioning of the hybrid

Li-ion battery system has only been addressed by Becker *et al.* [24], who have used the covariance matrix adaptation evolution strategy to optimize the pack design in terms of driving range, weight, and volume. However, concurrent consideration of lifetime and charging power requirements for optimal sizing of hybrid battery systems has not been addressed, previously. Higher C-rates will generally accelerate the aging of the Li-ion cells [25, 26]. Thus, it is challenging to simultaneously meet lifetime and charging power requirements with mono battery system designs [26]. The work carried out in this paper focuses on optimal sizing of hybrid battery systems targeting the two aforementioned objectives, which will be beneficial to the scalability of the battery pack design to cover a wider range of customers and EV requirements [27].

In the paper, we present an integrated model-based design framework for the optimal sizing of hybrid battery systems. The proposed framework considers different modeling levels from driving conditions and vehicle dynamics to the EV drivetrain and battery pack performance and lifetime models. The main aspect with which this paper distinguishes itself from other literature is optimal sizing of the hybrid battery system considering the cycle life and fast charging goals, separately from classical vehicle requirements such as weight, speed, driving range, acceleration, and load capacity. The study is undertaken considering a small-size electric car, namely Mitsubishi i-MiEV. The HE cells with NMC chemistry and HP cells with LTO chemistry are selected as inputs to the optimal sizing problem. A detailed analysis is also outlined that allows suitable voltage profiles for the HE and HP batteries with respect to the i-MiEV inverter DC-link voltage to be decided. The multi-objective optimization problem is then solved using a well-established evolutionary approach based on the genetic algorithm. The main contributions of this paper are as follows:

- A comprehensive model-based design framework is established, in which different models from driving cycle and vehicle dynamics to drivetrain models are considered to translate the EV driving cycle to the battery duty cycle in a top-down fashion. The framework is used to examine how different battery connections/configurations meet specific design targets.
- Unlike previous research [24], the suggested framework also includes the aging model of the batteries in order to consider life as a design objective. An effective approach is proposed to obtain the statistical distribution of different C-rates during the driving cycle and the accumulative aging is accordingly calculated. Furthermore, the charging speed is introduced to the framework as a new optimization variable.

- An effective approach for designing the hybridization architecture (positions of the HE and HP batteries and the DC-DC converter with respect to the DC-link) is outlined.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, the proposed model-based design approach including the modeling of EV forces, drivetrain, and performance/lifetime models of batteries are fulfilled. In Section 3, the battery hybridization architecture and energy management for power budgeting among HE and HP batteries are discussed. In Section 4, the multi-objective optimization problem and relevant constraints are established and parameterization of the genetic algorithm is fulfilled. The optimization results and discussions are provided in Section 5. Section 6 provides some discussions about the challenges and opportunities of the hybrid battery concept. Finally, the conclusions and some remarks for future work are provided in Section 7.

2- Proposed Model-Based Design Approach for Optimal Sizing of the Hybrid Battery

The proposed model-based design optimization framework is illustrated in Fig.1. In the first step, the EV driving cycles should be converted to appropriate battery pack duty cycles in order to measure the performance of different configurations. Consequently, this paper follows a model-based approach, in which different components are modeled from the system level to the components, i.e. the dynamics of the car on the road, gearbox and transmission system, electric motor, toward the inverter.

Fig. 1. Proposed framework for design optimization of the hybrid battery

When the required battery duty cycles are obtained, the profiles are used to measure the performance of different hybrid battery solutions, i.e. different connections and configurations (number of series and paralleled HE and HP cells). In practice, there will be thousands of different configurations-dependending on the series/parallel connections of the HE/HP cells- that should be examined to find the best architecture for the hybrid battery pack. However, analysis of all the

configurations is very time-consuming since the EV and battery performance and lifetime models require a long runtime. Especially as each battery configuration should be analyzed over the drive cycles which have long durations, an optimization algorithm to find the best hybrid battery configuration that minimizes a certain cost function is required. In the proposed framework, this is achieved using a well-established evolutionary optimization approach based on the genetic algorithm. In the following subsections, different parts of the proposed approach are presented in detail.

2.1. Transform Driving Cycle Data to Longitudinal Vehicle Forces

The driving cycles represent the speed of the EV versus time and were originally developed as a standard to measure vehicle emission and driving range, although they can also be used for simulation of the vehicle on the road. Various standard and unofficial driving cycles have been developed so far- Worldwide Harmonised Light Vehicles Test Procedure (WLTP), New European Driving Cycle (NEDC), and Urban Dynamometer Driving Schedule (UDDS) to name a few. The drive cycles are normally classified based on the driving conditions (city driving, highway driving, etc.) and/or the EV type (light EVs, electric trucks, etc.). A complete reference of the standard driving cycles is provided in [28]. In this paper, the NEDC and WLTP driving cycles are chosen to examine the battery pack design performance in road driving conditions. However, the EV driving cycle data should be transformed into battery duty cycles (power versus time data points) to determine the real loading conditions of the battery pack. To this end, the first step is to determine the vehicle's longitudinal forces in different driving conditions. In this paper, a simplified vehicle kinematics model is used to determine the tractive requirements of the EV powertrain [9]. The model represents different forces acting against EV as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Longitudinal forces acting against EV

These forces can be generally classified into four main components:

Rolling resistance force: The rolling resistance force is shown with F_r in Fig. 2. This is the force related to the friction between the road and EV tires, which can be expressed by:

$$F_r = K_r mg \cos \theta \quad (1)$$

with K_r being rolling resistance coefficient, m being the overall mass including EV mass and payload in kg, θ being the slope angle of the road in degree, and g being the gravitational constant equal to 9.8 m/s^2 .

Aerodynamic resistive force: Shown with F_a in Fig. 2, the aerodynamic force is a resistive force resulting from the friction between the airstream and EV. Higher driving speeds will generally result in higher aerodynamic losses as modeled in the following:

$$F_a = \frac{1}{2} \rho C_d A_f v^2 \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the air density in kg/m^3 , C_d is the coefficient of the drag force, A_f is the frontal area of the EV in m^2 , and v is the linear speed of the EV in m/s .

Wheel dynamics: Assuming J_{wheel} and r_{wheel} be the inertia and radius of the wheel and ω be the rotational speed, the rotational motion of the wheel can be written as follows:

$$J_{wheel} \frac{d\omega}{dt} = T_d - r_{wheel} F_d \quad (3)$$

where T_d and F_d are the motor torque and driving force, respectively. The nonlinear relationship between the driving force and the tire slip ratio can be expressed using the so-called magic formula [29]:

$$F_d = K_1 \sin \left(K_2 \tan^{-1} \left(K_3 \lambda - K_4 \left(K_3 \lambda - \tan^{-1} (K_3 \lambda) \right) \right) \right) \quad (4)$$

where K_1 to K_4 are dimensionless coefficients and their values for common road conditions can be easily found in the literature [29]. Likewise, λ is the wheel slip calculated as:

$$\lambda = r_{wheel} \omega - v \quad (5)$$

Transient force of the EV: This is the force required during acceleration and/or deceleration of the EV, which can be written according to second Newton's law as follows:

$$F_t = m \frac{dv}{dt} \quad (6)$$

In Fig. 2, F_g is the gradient force of the road which is neglected since θ will be zero during the drive cycle simulation. The tractive force will be zero whenever the EV is in cruising mode. According to (1) to (6), the following equation can be obtained:

$$F_d = m \frac{dv}{dt} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} \rho C_d A_f v^2 + K_r mg \cos \theta}_{\text{resistive forces}} \quad (7)$$

The driving force F_d can be translated to the driving torque T_d as follows [16]:

$$T_d = F_d \times r_{\text{wheel}} \quad (8)$$

Considering the gear ratio of the transmission system, the required output torque of the electric motor can be calculated as follows:

$$T_{\text{Motor}} = \frac{T_d}{\text{Gear Ratio}} \quad (9)$$

The effect of the drivetrain inertia is also considered using the Rotational Inertia block from MATLAB Simulink's Powertrain Blockset, which models an ideal mechanical rotational inertia. The values for the block parameters are given in Table 2.

2.2. Model of the Electric Motor and Inverter

The modeling of the motor-inverter is fulfilled based on MATLAB's look-up table which models efficiency contours in the torque-speed plane. The parameters of the efficiency map are chosen according to the 49 kW Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor (PMSM)/controller block from the Advanced Vehicle Simulator software known as ADVISOR[®] [30, 31]. The efficiency map shown in Fig. 3 governs the efficiency for a given set of motor torque and speed. The colored curves determine the efficiency that is achievable within a particular operating regime.

Fig. 3. The efficiency map of the inverter/motor considered for the EV simulation model [30, 31]

2.3. Battery Performance Model

Battery performance models are needed to evaluate the charge/discharge performance of different battery configurations. Different types of battery models have been proposed in the literature including physics-based models, Equivalent Circuit Models (ECMs), and data-driven models [32]. For battery pack sizing, a macroscopic modeling approach will suffice as the target is not to model the detailed dynamic behavior or to study the internal states of the batteries. Therefore, to avoid long runtime, a relatively simple battery ECM based on the so-called R_{int} structure is chosen for this study [32]. The R_{int} model structure is shown in Fig. 4. The model is composed of a variable voltage source V_{OC} and a series-connected resistance, which both are dependent on the State-of-Charge (SoC) and temperature (T). The voltage source and resistance replicate the open-circuit voltage and internal resistance of the battery, respectively. The current and terminal voltage are denoted with i and V_t , where the discharge current is assumed to be positive (conversely charge current is assumed to be negative). The terminal voltage of each cell can be obtained using the following formula:

$$V_t = V_{OC} - R \times i \quad (10)$$

Fig. 4. Battery performance model considered for the proposed model-based design approach

The ECM of Fig. 4 is presented for the general case to capture dependency on the cell temperature. However, in this paper, the ECM at $T = 25\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is considered for the optimization studies. Internal resistance was measured using the Hybrid Pulse Power Characteristic (HPPC) test considering five different charge/discharge current levels at different SoC conditions (from fully charged to a completely discharged cell). The pulse duration was set to 10 seconds and a rest period was considered after each charge/discharge step. A detailed description of the HPPC test protocol can be found in Annex C of IEC62660-1 [33]. Based on the five voltage responses recorded at each SoC condition, the charge/discharge resistances were calculated using the I-V five-point method [34], wherein the least squares algorithm was used for linear fitting to the HPPC test data. The slopes of the fitted lines were selected as the DC resistances at different SoC levels.

The voltage and current of the pack (V_{pack} and i_{pack}) can then simply be modeled considering the number of series (N_s) and parallel (N_p) connected cells as shown in Fig. 4. The SoC is updated using the Coulomb Counting (CC) technique with the following formula, while the Coulombic efficiency (η) of both HP and HE cells are considered to be 1, which is reasonably acceptable according to the literature [35].

$$SoC(t) = SoC(0) - \frac{1}{Q} \int_0^t \eta i(t) dt \quad (11)$$

2.4. Battery Lifetime Model

A well-designed hybridized pack can appropriately share and/or shift transients among the HE and HP cells to improve their life. In this paper, lifetime is introduced as a new optimization variable to the battery hybridization design. To this end, appropriate lifetime models should be

used to emulate battery cycle life degradation in the simulation environment. The lifetime of the considered NMC-based HE cells is modeled based on the empirical aging model proposed in [36, 37]. The life degradation of the HP cells with LTO chemistry is neglected due to the significantly higher cyclic stability of the studied HP cells reaching > 20,000 cycles [38].

The empirical lifetime model of the NMC cell is considered as a function of the temperature, C-rate, and amper-hour throughput as follows [36]:

$$Q_{Loss, \%} = (aT^2 + bT + c) e^{[(dT + e)I_{rate}]} Ah_{throughput} \quad (12)$$

where $Q_{Loss, \%}$ denotes the percentage of the capacity loss and a , b , c , d , and e are constant parameters, which can be obtained by fitting experimental battery aging data to the lifetime model (12). Likewise, T denotes the absolute temperature in centigrade, I_{rate} denotes the C-rate with which the battery is charged/discharged, and $Ah_{throughput}$ is the amount of A.h. of charging/discharging over the battery usage. The Ah-throughput of the battery can be calculated as follows:

$$Ah_{throughput} = N_{cycle} \times DoD \times Q \quad (13)$$

where N_{cycle} denotes the number of cycles and Q denotes the rated capacity of the HE battery. Considering the temperature condition to be $T = 25$ °C, the aging model can be rewritten as $Q_{Loss, \%} = a_1 \times e^{(a_2 \times I_{rate})} \times Ah_{throughput}$ in which a_1 and a_2 should be obtained by fitting the model to the experimental aging data. The curve fitting tool (cftool) of MATLAB and the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm is used for optimizing the parameters of the aging model. The parameters are calculated as shown in Table 1. The root means squares error of the fit is obtained at about 0.1. Fig. 5 visualizes the percentage of the capacity loss as a function of the C-rate and Depth-of-Discharge (DoD) [36]. It can be seen that higher C-rates will generally result in more capacity loss in the HE cells. The degradation is maximum at high C-rate and low DoD levels which is due to the excessive operation of the cells in high SoC regions. With the hybrid battery concept, high C-rates will be shifted from the HE cells to the HP cells, which will reduce the degradation of the HE battery as depicted in Fig. 5. The figure also shows that at lower C-rates, the aging of the HE cells will be less influenced by the DoD.

Table 1. Model parameters for the aging model of the considered NMC cells

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>
a_1	7.041×10^{-5}
a_2	0.7974

Fig. 5. Percentage of the capacity loss of the NMC-based HE cell under different C-rate and DoD conditions (over 1000 cycles and under temperature of 35 degC)

The considered lifetime model represents the percentage of the capacity loss for a specific C-rate (I_{rate}). However, during the drive cycle, different C-rates can be experienced by the battery. Therefore, the lifetime model is not directly applicable for calculating the capacity loss during the drive cycle. To address this problem, the current profile of the HE battery can be statistically analyzed to obtain the distribution of different C-rates over the considered drive cycle [8]. The distribution of different C-rates (absolute value of charge/discharge C-rate) and their frequency over the drive cycle can be shown in the form of histogram charts. Fig. 6 shows the histogram chart developed for a typical hybrid battery design considering HE (74.2 A.h./91s1p) and HP (20 A.h./50s1p) batteries, NEDC drive cycle, a typical EMS (as outlined in subsection 3.2), and Mitsubishi i-MiEV simulation model. For each C-rate condition k ($I_{rate}(k)$), the relevant $DoD(k)$ is also calculated. Then, the total ampere-hour throughput in different $I_{rate}(k)$ can be calculated as follows:

$$Ah_{throughput}(k) = N_{cycle} \times DoD(k) \times Q \quad (14)$$

Subsequently, the capacity loss under the corresponding $I_{rate}(k)$ is calculated by:

$$Q_{Loss, \%}(k) = a_1 \times e^{(a_2 \times I_{rate}(k))} \times Ah_{throughput}(k) \quad (15)$$

The total capacity loss $Q_{Loss,total}$ over the entire simulation time can then be obtained through summation of all capacity losses related to different C-rates:

$$Q_{Loss,total} = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{rate}} Q_{Loss,\%}(k) \quad (16)$$

where N_{rate} is the number of C-rates experienced in the drive cycle.

Fig. 6. Distribution of C-rates and their frequency in the NEDC drive cycle considering a typical hybrid battery system with an example EMS (based on subsection 3.2)

An analysis is fulfilled to select the proper C-rate interval for the calculation of the C-rate distributions. The C-rate distributions with three different C-rate intervals, i.e. 0.1C, 0.25C, and 0.5C are obtained for the WLTP driving cycle considering only the HE cells. The results are shown in Figs. 7 and 8.

Fig. 7. (a) Left axis: Magnitude of the HE cells discharge current under WLTP cycle. Right axis: C-rate levels experienced considering different C-rate intervals (b) zoomed view of the plot

Fig. 7 shows the current magnitude of the HE cells under the WLTP cycle (left axis) and the segmentation based on different C-rate intervals (right axis). The distribution of the C-rate intervals and their frequency in the WLTP cycle are shown in Fig. 8. The capacity losses with different C-rate intervals are calculated at about 14%, 13.6%, and 13.5% for the C-rate intervals

of 0.5C, 0.25C, and 0.1C, respectively. Generally, lower C-rate intervals will improve the fidelity of the calculations. However, smaller C-rate intervals will increase the runtime of the optimizer code. Notably, the difference between the calculated aging is also reasonably low at about 0.5%. Thus, to improve the optimization speed, the C-rates are established based on 0.5C intervals, i.e., the C-rate $\in [0,0.25)$ is equal to zero, C-rate $\in [0.25,0.75)$ is set to 0.5, C-rate $\in [0.75,1.25)$ is set to 1, and so forth.

Fig. 8. Distribution of the C-rate levels of the HE cell current under the WLTP cycle considering different C-rate intervals. Upper: 0.5C interval, Middle: 0.25C interval, Lower: 0.1C interval

It should be noted that the considered aging model does not distinguish between charge and discharge currents. However, in practice, high charge currents can have a higher influence on the battery degradation depending on the operating conditions such as temperature and SoC. In addition, the average SoC at which the discharge takes place also affects the aging of the cell. Therefore, in the follow-up works, it would be worthwhile to consider more accurate aging models that take these effects into account.

As mentioned, the Mitsubishi i-MiEV is considered to be the case study. The technical specifications and simulation parameters of the i-MiEV are listed in Table 2 [39].

Table 2. Simulation parameters of i-MiEV [39]

Parameter	Value
Curb Weight (m)	1185 kg
Wheel diameter ($2r_{wheel}$)	38.1 cm
Frontal Area (A_f)	2.14 m ²
Aerodynamic drag coefficient (C_d)	0.35
Tire rolling resistance (K_r)	0.012
Motor type	PMSM
Motor Power (kW)	50 kW
Transmission type	Single fixed reduction gear
Gear ratio	7.065
Rotational Inertia	0.1 kg.m ²
Torsional damping	0.001 N.m.s/rad
K_1	1
K_2	1.9
K_3	10
K_4	0.97
Driveline configuration	Real-Wheel Drive (RWD)
Wheelbase (in)	100.39
Battery type	Li-ion (LMO)
Number of cells	88
Cell configuration	Series
Battery pack voltage	330 V
Rated battery pack capacity	50 Ah
Rated battery pack energy	16 kWh

The established models are used to transform the drive cycle data to the required battery duty cycles. Typical results on the NEDC drive cycle are shown in Fig. 9.

Fig. 9. (a) NEDC drive cycle profile (b) Battery duty cycle in the NEDC drive cycle (c) kWh of the pack consumed over consecutive repetitions of the NEDC drive cycle (d) driving range of the modeled EV

Fig. 9(a) shows the standard NEDC drive cycle, which represents a combination of the city (until $t = 800$ s) and highway (from $t = 800$ s to end) driving conditions. Fig. 9(b) shows the obtained duty cycle of the battery pack in i-MiEV. The power profile will be used in the next section for sizing the hybrid battery pack. Figs. 9(c) and (d) also show the consumption and driving range of the i-MiEV. Based on the developed lifetime model and C-rate distribution in the NEDC drive cycle, the typical lifetime behavior of the utilized NMC-based HE cells at $T=25$ °C is plotted in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10. Remaining and lost capacity over 2000 cycles for a typical simulation scenario with the HE pack of 91s1p and HP pack of 50s1p in the NEDC drive cycle and considering MiEV as the case study

3- Hybridization Architecture and EMS

The architecture of the hybridization determines how the HE and HP packs will interface with each other as well as with the DC-link of the motor drive. This is important since it can impose a voltage constraint on the design optimization problem, e.g. when a pack is directly connected to the DC-link. Another important aspect regarding the hybridization concept is the EMS, which will determine the power budgeting among the HE and HP packs. The EMS determines how much power should be delivered by each pack at different operating conditions of the EV such as acceleration, braking, or cruising at high speeds. These aspects are discussed in more detail in the following subsections.

3.1. Hybridization Architecture

Different architectures can be used to connect two different ESSs [40]. From the topological standpoint, the battery hybridization design can be classified into two different groups, namely passive and active hybridization [41]. The simplest way for battery hybridization is the direct parallel connection of HE and HP packs, also known as passive hybridization [19]. In this topology, the HP cells have faster dynamics and thus act faster than the HE cells. This will provide support to the HE cells during the electrical charge/discharge transients caused by braking/acceleration conditions. Therefore, the HP cells will behave as a low-pass filter across the HE cells, which will help to shift the peak charge/discharge currents thereby reducing the degradation of HE cells. Nonetheless, with passive hybridization, the full potential of hybridization cannot be realized due to two reasons: Firstly, the HE and HP packs are required to have the same voltage profile, which will limit design flexibility. Secondly, transient recovery currents will be drawn by the HP cells after large discharge incidents, which has a negative effect on the HE cells. A better solution is active hybridization, in which power electronic converters will be used to interface the HE/HP batteries with the DC-link. Regarding active hybridization, three main hybridization architectures are shown in Fig. 11.

Fig. 11. Different possible architectures for battery hybridization (a) HE battery directly connected to the DC-link (b) HP battery connected to the DC-link (c) HE and HP batteries connected to DC-link via separate DC-DC converters

Fig. 11(a) shows the option with the HE battery directly connected to the DC-link of the motor drive and the HP battery connected to the HE battery via a bidirectional DC-DC converter. This topology puts a voltage constraint on the number of series-connected HE cells (which should meet the DC-link voltage requirement). Likewise, the converter rating needs to match the power requirement of the HP battery, which will increase the size and weight of the converter and its cooling system. The second option is shown in Fig. 11(b) and it is the opposite connection of the first option. Similarly, this topology puts a voltage constraint on the number of series-connected HP cells, which might restrict the feasible solution space in the design optimization problem. The third option is shown in Fig. 11(c), where both HE and HP batteries are connected to the DC-link via separate DC-DC converters. This design offers maximum design flexibility; however, it

requires two full-size converters, which will increase the overall implementation cost. The choice of suitable topology depends on the final design targets and limitations, as well as the specifications of the HE/HP cells selected for the hybridization. Here, a straightforward optimization is undertaken to decide the topology that can provide the best trade-off among the considered design targets, i.e. energy density and fast charging capability of the hybrid battery.

The specifications of the HE and HP cells considered are listed in Table 3. In Table 4, the internal resistance values at $T=25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are provided. The maximum charge/discharge current values were calculated using I-V five-point method. The charge/discharge power limits were calculated based on the maximum current values and upper/lower voltage limits of the cells (maximum power points are the product of the maximum current and limit voltage).

Table 3. Specifications of the HE and HP cells considered for hybridization

Parameter	HE	HP
Rated capacity	74.2 A.h.	20 A.h.
Nominal voltage	3.65 V	2.3 V
Voltage range	2.75 to 4.25 V	1.5 to 2.7 V
Cathode/anode	NMC/graphite	Unknown/LTO
Energy density	642 Wh/L	176 Wh/L
Charge power density	320 W/L	1698 W
Discharge power density	1902 W/L	1698 W
Weight	930 gr	540 gr
Volume	0.422 L	0.271 L

Table 4. Discharge internal resistance values at $T=25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

SoC (%)	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90
HE cell resistance (m Ω)	1.95	1.65	1.58	1.51	1.52	1.58	1.59	1.61	1.62
HP cell resistance (m Ω)	1.05	0.72	0.58	0.57	0.57	0.6	0.59	0.58	0.59

As seen in Table 3, the HE cell has a higher energy density but lower charging power compared with the HP cell. To achieve the shortest charging time, the pack should be composed of only HP cells. On the other hand, to achieve maximum energy density, HE cells should merely be used in the pack design. Thus, a trade-off is needed to simultaneously optimize energy density and charging power. The following cost function is established to obtain the best hybridization architecture (positions of the HE and HP cells with respect to the DC-link) in terms of design targets:

$$CF = (500 - Wh / L)^2 + \gamma(100 - \%SoC)^2 \quad (17)$$

The cost function integrates two different design targets: 1) 500 Wh/L energy density for the hybrid battery and 2) fast charging of the hybrid battery within 6 minutes. These numbers are just examples to compare different hybridization options. It should be noted that the pack volume factor (consideration of cooling system, holders, etc.) is neglected for simplicity, however, it can easily be introduced to the design when required. The parameter γ determines the weight of each design target. When γ is zero, only the energy density will be considered in the problem while a very large γ value gives more weight to the charging power. For all hybridization architectures of Fig. 11, the cost function is solved considering a large combination of cells configurations as well as for γ values ranging from 0 to 100. For different settings, the results of the minimized cost are obtained and plotted as shown in Fig. 12. It is observable that for very small or very large values of γ , cases (b) and (c) end up with almost similar results in contrast to case (a) in which the achievable charging speed is considerably lower at large values of γ . This is due to the fact that in case (a) the HE cells are directly connected to the DC-link and thus, the HE pack voltage should comply with the voltage of the DC-link in the EV. This necessitates using a large number of series connected HE cells, which will increase the energy/power density of the overall system thereby reducing the percentage of the charged SoC.

The results also show that both targets cannot be obtained at the same time, however, the intersection of the curves indicates a compromise point between achievable energy density and charging time. In the first scenario, the hybrid pack will have a relatively high energy density of around 450 Wh/L while only about 30% of the pack can be charged within 6 minutes. In the second scenario, the achievable design targets seem to be more balanced showing a trade-off with about 300 Wh/L and 60% charging of pack. The result of the third scenario is slightly better than scenario 2; however, the latter is favored here since it requires only 1 power converter (improvement with an additional converter is negligible).

According to this analysis, the second hybridization architecture is chosen for the study. It should be noted that this result may change when different HE/HP cells are chosen or when different design targets are considered for the battery hybridization concept. It should also be clarified that the focus here is to design the overall architecture to determine how the HE/HP batteries should interface with the DC-link and a detailed discussion about the type of converter and/or converter design is not within the scope of the work. In the design optimization process, the DC-DC converter is modeled only with an input-output power relationship with the efficiency of ξ .

Fig. 12. Obtained trade-off among design targets with different hybridization architectures (a) HE battery connected to DC-link (b) HP battery connected to DC-link (c) HE and HP batteries connected with interface converters

3.2. EMS Scheme

The EMS defines the strategy for controlling the power flow of the HE and HP batteries. In other words, it determines the power budgeting between different cells in different operating conditions of the EV, e.g. during the acceleration, regenerative braking, or cruising. It can be designed to optimize some specific performance criteria, such as the lifetime of batteries. The EMSs can be broadly classified as 1) rule-based methods and 2) optimization-based methods. The rule-based approach can be, for example, based on Fuzzy logic or a deterministic approach. The

optimization-based approach can be based on 1) real-time optimization with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm or model predictive control (MPC) or 2) global optimization such as linear or dynamic programming. The EMSs for hybrid ESSs are fully reviewed in [42]. In this paper, a straightforward rule-based EMS is chosen for optimal sizing of the hybrid pack. The utilized EMS is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. The EMS utilized in the proposed hybrid battery design optimization framework

Algorithm	
1:	if $P_{NEDC} > P_{max}$
2:	$P_{HE} = P_{max}$
3:	$P_{HP} = P_{NEDC} - P_{max}$
4:	else if $P_{NEDC} \leq P_{max} \ \&\& \ P_{NEDC} > 0$
5:	$P_{HE} = P_{NEDC}$
6:	$P_{HP} = 0$
7:	else
8:	$P_{HE} = 0$
9:	$P_{HP} = P_{NEDC}$
10:	end if
11:	end if

In Table 5, P_{NEDC} denotes the required power during the NEDC drive cycle (similarly P_{WLTP} shows the required power in the WLTP cycle), P_{HP} is the power of the HP battery, and P_{HE} is the power of the HE battery. Based on this strategy, up to a maximum demand power of P_{max} , the EMS will supply the power with only the HE battery and the set-point for the power of the HP battery will be almost zero. When the power demand exceeds P_{max} , the reference power of the HE battery will be set to P_{max} and the rest of the demanded power will be supplied by the HP battery. Likewise, the regeneration power is completely treated by the HP battery. The best value of P_{max} is determined by an optimization study described in the next section. If the EV is driven at a constant speed with $P < P_{max}$, the EV will end up with a completely depleted HE battery while the HP battery will not be used at all. Therefore, in practice, the EMS should take into account the SoC of the HE and HP batteries to achieve effective energy utilization. Nonetheless, the considered driving cycles in this study are composed of a mix of different dynamic driving conditions such as acceleration, cruising, and braking and thus, such condition is not probable with these driving cycles. As will be explained in Section 4, the introduction of the driving range requirement will also enforce solutions that will lead to effective utilization of the overall pack energy. Thus, the simple strategy is selected considering that the EMS is not the focus of this paper.

4- Formulation of the Optimization Problem

As illustrated in Fig. 1, the multi-objective optimizer is needed to obtain the optimal sizing of the hybrid battery pack. The optimizer sends selected hybrid battery configurations to the vehicle simulation layer and upon receiving the results, scores the solutions considering the fitness function and the design objectives, i.e. weight of the battery, charging power, as well as lifetime. Then, based on the results, the optimizer decides the next battery configuration to be evaluated in the next iteration of the optimization. This process will continue until a certain stop criterion is met, e.g. when the optimizer has converged or when a predetermined amount of time and/or iterations has elapsed. It is impossible to form a closed-loop formulation with guaranteed differentiability for the considered multi-objective optimization framework. Therefore, the genetic algorithm is used as a well-known heuristic optimization method. The flowchart of the considered genetic algorithm is shown in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. Flowchart of the genetic algorithm for hybrid pack design optimization

In Fig. 13, the term population refers to a set of initial solutions (chromosomes) for the configuration of the hybrid battery. The size of the population is denoted with N . The chromosomes are composed of four genes, which are the reference power P_{max} in the EMS algorithm, the number of parallel HP cells ($N_{P,HP}$), number of series HE cells ($N_{S,HE}$), and the number of the parallel HE cells ($N_{P,HE}$), respectively. The number of series-connected HP cells ($N_{S,HP}$) is already known (and thus not considered as an optimization variable) due to the required voltage constraint at the DC-link of the inverter. Selection, crossover, and mutation are the genetic algorithm's special terms inspired by natural evolution to synthesize new populations. More details about the genetic algorithm can be found in [43, 44]. Three objectives to minimize the weight, charging time, and battery degradation are considered as follows:

$$J_1 = f_1(P_{ref}, N_{s,HE}, N_{p,HE}, N_{p,HP}) = mass_{battery}^2 \quad (18)$$

$$J_2 = f_2(P_{ref}, N_{s,HE}, N_{p,HE}, N_{p,HP}) = (60 - SoC_{ch})^2 \quad (19)$$

$$J_3 = f_3(P_{ref}, N_{s,HE}, N_{p,HE}, N_{p,HP}) = Q_{Loss}^2 \quad (20)$$

where $mass_{battery}$ denotes the overall weight of the hybrid battery pack considering the HE and HP cells, overhead weight (bus bars, BMS, TMS, etc.), and the weight of the DC-DC converter. The overhead weight is calculated using a scale factor of 1.45, which is obtained based on the pack-to-cell weight ratio in the Mitsubishi i-MiEV [39]. Likewise, the weight of the DC-DC converter is calculated based on a power density of 1.2 kW/kg and the rating of the DC-DC converter will be calculated to comply with the power rating of the HE battery.

Equation (19) sets a goal to charge 60% of the pack within 6 minutes. The objective functions are then combined into a multi-objective optimization function J as follows:

$$\text{Minimize } J = J_1 + \alpha J_2 + \beta J_3 \quad (21)$$

where α and β are coefficients that determine the weights and relative importance of different objectives in the optimization problem. The coefficient α determines the weight of the charging power target while β determines the weight of the capacity loss (aging) target. Higher values of the coefficient will increase the importance of the particular cost function while a lower value will reduce the importance. For example, a higher value of β compared to α forces the optimizer toward solutions that have less charging power but a longer lifetime. In this paper, the charging speed, and weight are considered more important performance indicators and thus, the lifetime is penalized

by a factor of 0.5 to facilitate solutions that provide better charging power and lower weights. The values of the weighting coefficients are listed in Table 6.

The problem is subjected to some constraints which are described in the following:

DC-link voltage constraint: The HP cells are directly connected to the dc-link of the motor inverter. Therefore, the number of series-connected HP cells should be determined to comply with the voltage of the DC-link. The following condition should thus be satisfied:

$$N_{S,HP} \times V_{HP,rated} = V_{DC-link} \quad (22)$$

where $V_{HP,rated}$ denotes the rated voltage of the HP cell and $V_{DC-link}$ is the rated DC-link voltage.

Energy constraint: Depending on the car size and requirements, the energy of the pack should be higher than a specified value:

$$(N_{S,HP} \times N_{P,HP}) \times E_{HP} + (N_{S,HE} \times N_{P,HE}) \times E_{HE} \geq E_{demand} \quad (23)$$

where E_{HP} , E_{HE} , and E_{demand} are the rated energy of the HP cell, the rated energy of the HE cell, and the energy demand, respectively.

Driving range: Depending on the requirements, the driving range of the EV should be higher than a specific value H as follows:

$$Drive\ range \geq H \quad (24)$$

Discharge power: The discharge power of the hybrid pack should be higher than the required peak power in different driving profiles as follows:

$$(N_{S,HP} \times N_{P,HP}) \times P_{HP} + (N_{S,HE} \times N_{P,HE}) \times P_{HE} \geq P_{demand} \quad (25)$$

where P_{HP} denotes the rated discharge power of HP cell, P_{HE} denotes the rated discharge power of the HE cell, and P_{demand} denotes the demanded power by MiEV in the driving cycle.

Volume of the pack: The volume of the pack should be lower than the maximum volume required to integrate into the i-MiEV:

$$(N_{S,HP} \times N_{P,HP}) \times Vol_{HP} + (N_{S,HE} \times N_{P,HE}) \times Vol_{HE} \geq Vol_{max} \quad (26)$$

where Vol_{HP} , Vol_{HE} , and Vol_{max} are the volume of the HP cell, the volume of the HE cell, and the maximum volume, respectively.

5- Results and Discussions

The i-MiEV drivetrain simulation is carried out in MATLAB/SIMULINK. Likewise, the optimization algorithms are implemented using MATLAB m-files. The simulation data and codes are uploaded to the Mendeley data repository [45]. The simulation parameters of i-MiEV and the specifications of the considered HE and HP cells are provided in Tables 2 to 4, respectively. The number of series-connected HP cells is set to 144. Based on the sizing constraints, the ranges of the optimization variables are considered as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 \text{ kW} &\leq P_{\max} < 30 \text{ kW} \\ 1 &\leq N_{P,HP}, N_{P,HE} < 10 \\ 1 &\leq N_{S,HE} < 200 \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

The initial SoC values for both HE and HP batteries are set to 100%. Likewise, the minimum and maximum operating SoC limits are set to 10% and 100%, respectively. The simulations are fulfilled at $T=25$ °C. Other parameters of the optimization are specified in Table 6.

Table 6. Simulation parameters

Parameter	Value
Number of genes	4
Population size	100
Maximum iterations	50
Crossover rate	30%
Mutation rate	50%
Elites' generation rate	20%
α	1
β	0.5
H	100 km
T	25 °C
Vol_{max}	110 L
$V_{DC-link}$	330 V
E_{demand}	20 kWh
P_{demand}	50 kW
ξ	0.95
Coulombic efficiency	1

The whole optimization takes on average about 95 minutes on a computer with Core i5 2.11 GHz processors and 16 GB RAM. The evolution of the fitness function throughout a typical optimization scenario is shown in Fig. 14.

Fig. 14. Evolution of the cost function throughout the optimization runtime

According to the optimization results considering the NEDC driving cycle, the optimal design variables are obtained as $P_{max} = 4870$ W, $N_{P,HP} = 2$, $N_{S,HE} = 31$, and $N_{P,HE} = 2$. The overall weight of the hybrid battery is obtained 320 kg, which can be charged up to 58% within 6 minutes. The capacity loss (due to cyclic aging) of the HE battery is about 3.7% after 2000 NEDC cycles. Likewise, with the newly designed battery pack, iMiEV can drive 166 km on the NEDC drive cycle. The optimization variables for the WLTP case are obtained as $P_{max} = 6526$ W, $N_{P,HP} = 2$, $N_{S,HE} = 8$, and $N_{P,HE} = 3$. The optimization over WLTP yields a 19.7 kWh hybrid pack with an overall 268 kg weight and 88 L volume, which can be charged up to 73% within 6 minutes. With the newly designed pack, the i-MiEV can drive 119 km on the WLTP cycle. In the WLTP case, the capacity loss of the HE cells will be 9.8% after 2000 WLTP cycles, which translates to > +45,000 km increase in the achievable driving warranty compared to the battery with only HE cells and considering the End-of-Life (EoL) criterion of 70%. The optimization results are summarized in Table 7. To draw a comparison, sizing with the mono-battery system, i.e. when HE or HP batteries are individually used is also fulfilled and the results are provided in Table 7.

Table 7. Summary of the pack sizing results

	Configuration	Weight	Volume	Pack Energy	Drive range	Charging speed*	Degradation**	Achievable mileage***	P_{max}
Optimized pack (NEDC)	HP: 144S2P / HE: 31S2P	320 kg	104 L	30 kWh	166 km	Up to 58%	3.76 %	175,000 km	4870 W
Optimized pack (WLTP)	HP:144S2P / HE: 8S3P	268 kg	88 L	19.7 kWh	119 km	Up to 73%	9.8 %	147,000 km	6526 W
HE only (WLTP)	91S1P	124 kg	38.4 L	24.6 kWh	150 km	Up to 18 %	14 %	100,000 km	N.R.
HP only (WLTP)	144S3P	340 kg	117 L	19.9 kWh	123 km	Up to 100%	N.R.	N.R.	N.R.

* Amount of charged SoC (in %) within 6 minutes. ** Degradation is calculated over 2000 cycles. *** Until EOL of 70% of initial capacity

It can be seen that the battery pack formed with only HE cells achieves the best performance in terms of weight/energy density and the worst performance in terms of degradation and charging speed. On the other hand, the battery pack formed with only HP cells achieves the best charging performance, however, the weight and energy density of the pack is the worst among different options. The results confirm that the hybrid battery concept provides demonstrable benefits in terms of energy, lifetime, and charging power. The required number of cycles of the HP cells is calculated at around 1085 and 1225 cycles for the solutions obtained under NEDC and WLTP, respectively, which is equivalent to about 2.5% and 4% drop in the capacity of the HP cells at 25 °C [46]. The study of the calendric aging of the LTO cells is fulfilled in [47]. The study shows that even in harsh conditions such as very high SoC levels or at high temperatures up to 60 °C the decrease in the capacity and increase of the internal resistance are respectively limited to -4% and +10% after 12 months, which will be reasonable for the EV applications. The results and references reconfirm the sufficiency of the overall lifetime of the LTO cells for the proposed hybrid battery solutions.

The fuel economy of the hybrid battery pack is obtained at 169.5 Wh/km and 176.73 Wh/km for the NEDC and WLTP cases, respectively. This is slightly higher than the mono battery systems which achieve a fuel economy of about 169 Wh/km on the WLTP cycle. The slightly higher energy consumption of the hybrid battery can be attributed to the power losses of the DC-DC converter.

The simulation results of the iMiEV with the optimized battery pack over the NEDC driving cycle are shown in Figs. 15 and 16. Fig. 15(a) shows the overall current profile in the NEDC driving cycle. As seen in Fig. 15(b), the current profile of the HE cells is smoothed by the EMS resulting in saving of the ampere-hour throughput in transient conditions. The HE battery provides only the small average power required by MiEV in less-demanding driving conditions such as cruising at low speeds. The voltage and SoC of the HE cells are also shown in Figs. 15(c) and (d), respectively. The simulation results of the HP cells are shown in Fig. 16. As seen in Fig. 16(a), the HP battery provides peak power demands when the EV is in acceleration mode or when cruising at a high speed. The negative current in the NEDC cycle shows the regeneration process during the deceleration/braking of the MiEV. The regeneration is fulfilled only by HP cells. However, the EMS can easily be modified to involve HE cells when for example the SoC of the HP battery is too high to receive additional energy.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Fig. 15. HE battery simulation results (a) Overall battery current in the NEDC driving profile (b) Current of the HE cells (c) Voltage of the HE cells (d) SoC of the HE cells in consecutive simulations of the NEDC cycle

Fig. 16. HP battery simulation results (a) Current of the HP cells (b) Voltage of the HP cells (c) SoC of the HP cells over consecutive NEDC cycles

To show the robustness of the proposed optimized solution, it should be tested under drive cycles different than the drive cycle used for design optimization. To this end, the battery pack optimized under the WLTP cycle is tested under two other drive cycles, i.e. Federal Test Procedure (FTP) also known as FTP75, and the US06 which is a high acceleration aggressive driving schedule. The degradation in the capacity of the HE battery after 2000 driving cycles is obtained at about 7% and 4.8% for the FTP75 and US06 cycles, respectively. Likewise, with the WLTP-based hybrid pack, the MiEV drives about 116 km and 102 km under FTP75 and US06, respectively. The results show that the performances of the proposed solution under the considered drive cycles are satisfactory. The simulation results under the FTP75 and UDDS drive cycles are shown in Figs. 17 and 18.

Fig. 17. (a) Driving cycles used to optimize and validate the proposed solution (b) Battery duty cycles under different driving cycles (c) Power budgeting with the proposed hybrid solution under the US06 driving cycle

Fig. 17(a) shows the WLTP, FTP75, and US06 driving cycles while the corresponding battery duty cycles are shown in Fig. 17(b). In Fig. 17(c), the power budgeting results under the US06 drive cycle are depicted. As seen, the peak powers are effectively shifted from HE cells toward the

HP cells to reduce the C-rate and degradation of the HE battery. Simulation results related to the current, voltage, and SoC of the HE and HP batteries under the US06 drive cycle are provided in Fig. 18.

Fig. 18. (a) Current profiles of the HE and HP batteries under US06 driving cycle (b) Voltage and SoC of the HE battery under US06 drive cycle (c) Voltage and SoC of the HP battery under US06 drive cycle

The C-rates of the HE cell is restricted below 1C while for HP cells C-rates with up to 2C are observed. All the regenerative braking current is also handled by the HP cells to reduce the HE cell degradation. The results confirm the correctness of the proposed design and the considered EMS.

To further reveal the benefit of the battery hybridization, the hybrid pack optimizer is solved by considering different weighting factors and the obtained results are plotted and shown in Fig. 19. The values of weighting factors are considered to be between 0 and 1.

Fig. 19. Achievable targets when the optimizer is used with weighting factors settings (a) Capacity loss (b) Charging speed (c) Weight

Fig. 19 reveals that by tuning the weighting coefficients in the multi-objective optimizer one can easily maneuver to adjust the achievable design factors depending on the specific EV requirements. The flexibility to realize a wider range of requirements, as Fig. 19 confirms, is a major benefit of using such hybrid battery systems.

6- Further discussions: opportunities, challenges, and cost analysis

The battery hybridization concept combines the complementary advantageous features of two different battery types. Compared to the HE cells, HP cells outperform in terms of operating temperature window, charge/discharge power capability, and lifetime. On the other hand, the HE cells are more energy-dense, which can improve the driving range and reduce the weight of the EV. The hybridization concept decouples the energy and power resulting in more design flexibility to achieve a good optimum between different design objectives that are challenging to be met, simultaneously. It makes it easier to meet certain power and energy requirements for a wide range of EVs and use cases. Advanced energy management strategies are implementable in the cloud space which will provide the opportunity to decide the optimal share of power for HE and HP batteries based on advanced algorithms and optimization techniques. The battery pack hybridization combined with an effective EMS can improve the battery energy efficiency and lifetime and the overall EV performance. The concept review of the cloud BMSs is comprehensively addressed in [48].

While the advantages of hybridization are the focus of this paper, it should be noted that some challenges might arise during the implementation of the concept. These issues are discussed in the following:

- 1) Normally, performance/aging/safety tests are needed to design algorithms for the battery management system (BMS) [49]. With hybridization, extra effort will be needed for testing two different batteries and to design and develop the BMS algorithms. These costs will only be associated with the research & development phase though.
- 2) An additional power converter is needed to interface the HE and HP batteries. This will also lead to an increment in the overall cost.

Regarding the second point, a cost analysis is carried out to provide a detailed assessment of the total price. The considered HE and HP cells were purchased at 370 €/kWh and 934 €/kWh. Considering the DC-DC converter to be priced at 45 €/kW, the cost of the converter will be about 1080 € for the hybrid pack solution obtained under WLTP. A typical cell-to-pack cost ratio of 70:30 can also be considered to account for the cost of BMS, TMS, welding, etc. The performance and cost comparisons related to three different scenarios, i.e. the proposed hybrid pack, pack formed with HE cells only, and pack with HP cells only are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Performance and cost comparison between the hybrid solution and the solutions based on the single cell types

Pack option*	Energy	Weight	Fast charging**	Life	Cell cost	DC-DC converter cost	Pack cost
Hybrid	19.7 kWh	268 kg	70%	147,000 km	15,380 €	1080 €	23,051 €
NMC only	24.6 kWh	124 kg	5%	100,000 km	9120 €	0 €	13,000 €
LTO only	19.9 kWh	340 kg	100%	Not relevant	18,560 €	0 €	26,500 €

* All based on WLTP drive cycle. ** % charge within 6 minutes

The cost analysis shows that the price of the pack with only the NMC cells will be the lowest while the pack formed only with the LTO cells will be the most expensive solution. The cost of the hybrid pack is between the two previous options. The price of the DC-DC converter is negligible compared to the battery cell cost. While this result shows that the hybrid solution might not be necessarily the cheapest option, it is a reasonable solution if we aim to achieve fast charging beside a good lifetime and low weight. While LTO cells are more expensive in terms of €/kWh, they usually come at a lower €/kW, which is important considering that for many EV models fast charging of the cells is a key market requirement. The price per kW (charging power) is 740 €/kW and 93 €/kW for the HE and HP cells, respectively. It will considerably challenge the economy of the design if one aims to achieve fast charging capability by using only the HE cells. In addition to the fast-charging advantage of the hybrid pack, the cost can also be justified if we consider the benefits in the extended life. In Fig. 20, different options are ranked on a basis of 1 to 3 (1 being the worst option and 3 being the best). The figure intuitively suggests a better trade-off between the four design targets is achieved using the hybrid pack.

Fig. 20. Radar plot for ranking of the design options considering lifetime, charging speed, weight, and energy density

7- Conclusions and Future Work

In this work, a model-based optimization framework is developed to design a hybrid battery pack concept for EVs. The multi-objective optimization involves three different objectives regarding the weight, charging power, and lifetime of the pack. The HE battery with NMC chemistry and HP battery with LTO chemistry are chosen for the hybrid pack concept. The genetic algorithm is used to solve the optimization problem considering i-MiEV as a case study. The results confirm the effectiveness of the proposed concept. The optimized pack provides 119 km of driving range on the WLTP drive cycle while it can be fast-charged up to about 70% within only 6 minutes. Compared to the pack with only HE cells, the degradation is 4.2% lower over 2000 WLTP cycles, which translates to $> +40,000$ km in achievable driving warranty considering the EOL criterion of 70%. The obtained results demonstrate that the proposed hybrid battery system provides a better trade-off considering the energy and power constraints.

The proposed concept opens door to several research paths. The following topics can be interesting research directions:

- For future work, it will be interesting to consider the effect of cell selection on the optimization and performance of the hybrid battery pack. The cells are the input to the optimization problem; however, it will also be interesting to optimize for the cells, i.e. to obtain the best set of HE and HP cells that will maximize the design optimality. Regarding the latter, the authors have been investigating and soon will disseminate a systematic approach to develop decision matrices for the selection of the HE/HP cells.
- It would be worthwhile to use a more detailed aging model of both HE and HP cells in future studies to consider the mixed degradation effects related to cyclic and calendar aging under different conditions.
- Other design objectives could also be analyzed within the hybrid battery context. For example, it could be interesting to optimize the pack to minimize the drivetrain power losses including the hybrid battery and the interface DC-DC converter. The detailed cost analysis by taking into account the operating costs and EoL costs (apart from the investment cost) can also be fulfilled in the future.
- Last but not least, more realistic and advanced EMSs would be interesting to be developed within the proposed design optimization framework, e.g., by considering the SoC values of the HE and HP batteries, using advanced optimization methods for EMS, considering limp home mode strategy to operate under abnormal condition, etc.

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